

In such membranes, t_p is of the order 0.2, and hence, from equation (10),

$$d \cong 0.1 \text{ micron,}$$

which is in good agreement with the postulated thickness³ of the dense surface-layer of such membranes.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III) Oxidation of Levulinic Acid

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THE earlier studies on alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) oxidation of the organic compounds showed that the anions derived from the organic acids are oxidised by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion¹. However, Speakman and Waters² have suggested complex mechanism for the oxidation of aldehydes, ketones and paraffins. Singh and co-workers³ suggested that the oxidation of formaldehyde takes place by free radical mechanism. The present study aims at getting more definite information regarding the mechanism of oxidation of levulinic acid by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III).

Experimental

The sample of levulinic acid was of E. Merck grade and all other chemicals were of G.R. (S. Merck). The rate of oxidation was determined titrimetrically³.

Stoichiometry :

The equivalents of hexacyanoferrate(III) required per mole of levulinic acid were found to be four. The acetic and formic acids were identified chromatographically. The stoichiometry of the reaction may be given as

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Results

The results obtained under different conditions are reported in Table 1. The constant value of pseudo first order rate constant shows that the order with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III) is one. Pseudo first order rate constants obtained at different concentrations of both levulinic acid and hydroxide ion were directly proportional to the concentrations of levulinic acid and hydroxide ion respectively showing thereby first order dependence of the reaction on each levulinic acid and hydroxide ion. This is also confirmed by constant values of $k_1/[\text{OH}^-][\text{Substrate}]$ given in the last column of the table. The work has been carried out at three more temperatures and results are given in Table 1. The effect of ionic strength of the medium was also studied and results are given in the table. The energy of activation was found to be 12.1 K cal mol⁻¹.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [REACTANTS] ON REACTION RATE

Temp. °C	10 ³ [Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻] M	10 ³ [LA] M	10 ³ [OH ⁻] M	(μ) M	10 ³ k ₁ min ⁻¹	k ₁ K M ⁻² min ⁻¹
35	1.25	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.76	—
35	1.44	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.79	—
35	1.66	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.76	—
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.73	—
35	2.50	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.69	—
35	3.34	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.73	—
35	4.00	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.71	—
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.10	1.06	—
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.125	1.40	—
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.20	2.00	—
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.25	2.44	—
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.30	2.76	—
35	2.00	0.80	3.20	0.125	0.60	2.30
35	2.00	1.00	3.20	0.125	0.72	2.25
35	2.00	1.25	3.20	0.125	0.96	2.40
35	2.00	1.40	3.20	0.125	1.10	2.45
35	2.00	1.60	3.20	0.125	1.18	2.34
35	2.00	2.00	3.20	0.125	1.53	2.39
35	2.00	3.00	3.20	0.125	2.28	2.37
35	2.00	2.00	2.50	0.125	1.15	2.55
35	2.00	2.00	4.00	0.125	1.90	2.37
35	2.00	2.00	5.00	0.125	2.28	2.28
35	2.00	2.00	6.66	0.125	3.24	2.43
35	2.00	2.00	10.00	0.125	4.86	2.43
30	1.25	2.00	3.20	0.07	0.47	—
40	1.25	2.00	3.20	0.07	1.12	—
45	1.25	2.00	3.20	0.07	1.70	—

LA → Levulinic Acid.

Discussion

In the light of above observations, the probable

scheme of oxidation may be considered as follows :

The rate of oxidation could obviously be given by rate of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate(III) as shown in step (II), i.e.,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = k_2 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}][\bar{\text{S}}] \quad \dots \text{(1)}$$

The net rate of oxidation of levulinic acid thus can be obtained on substituting the value of $[\bar{\text{S}}]$ from step (I) in eqn. (1) and is given as

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = k_2 K [\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] \quad \dots \text{(2)}$$

where K is the equilibrium constant and S is substrate anion. At constant [S] and [OH⁻], $k_2 K [\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]$ can be replaced by pseudo first order rate constant k_1 .

The observed first order dependence of the reaction on each hexacyanoferrate(III), levulinic acid and hydroxide ion concentration is obvious from the equation (2). The rate determining step would involve interaction between two negatively charged ions [obvious from step (II)]. For this step a positive salt effect is expected. The effect of ionic strength of the medium on reaction rate was studied by employing different concentrations of potassium chloride (Table I). Our experimental results are in complete agreement with the above facts.

In most of the oxidation reactions hexacyanoferrate(III) resembles Cu(II) which involves free radical formation and rapidly oxidises it⁴⁻⁶. Hexacyanoferrate(III)-hexacyanoferrate(II) system, which has higher redox potential than Cu(II)-Cu(I), substantiates better possibility of the rapid oxidation of the free radical with hexacyanoferrate(III) in the alkaline medium and the rapid oxidation of the free radicals might completely mask the polymerisation. Sometimes the vinyl compounds themselves are oxidised under the experimental conditions used

and the test for free radicals fails⁷. Moreover, no spectrophotometric test for complex formation was observed.

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Baeyer-Villiger Oxidation of Steroidal Ketones-V

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IN continuation of our reports on Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of steroidal ketones¹⁻⁴, we subjected compounds (I-IV) to perbenzoic acid oxidation in the presence of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, as catalyst. A number of anticipated products were successfully isolated from 4-substituted derivatives of cholest-5-en-3-one (I-II) and cholest-4-en-3-one (III-IV).

